

Annamalai Journal of Management

"A Journal of Virtue"

February 2008

ISSN - 0974 - 0406

Volume - 2 • Issue - 1

V. SUMATHY, M.B.A., M.Phil., Ph.D.
Assistant Professor
Department of Business Administration
Annamalai University,
Annamalai Nagar - 608 002.
Research Articles.

Case Studies

Doctoral Dissertation Abstracts

Paper Callfor

Forthcoming Programmes

AU-AJM

Journal of Virtue

www.annamalaiuniversity.ac.in

CONTENTS

SUCCESSION PLANNING ISSUES FOR FAMILY BUSINESSES <i>Deepshikha Bhargava</i>	1
CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY – CHANGING PARADIGMS IN MANAGEMENT <i>M.L.Gopichander</i>	8
BUSINESS SCHOOL STRATEGY: DEVELOPING LEADERS FIT TO LEAD <i>Dr. Jonathan Smith and John Rayment</i>	14
INTUITIVE MOVEMENT SENSING AND FAST MOSAICING BY CORNER DETECTION AND 3-D MULTIBASELINING <i>Ms.R.Kalaivaazhi</i>	22
CONTRASTING CUSTOMERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE CONVENTIONAL AND ISLAMIC BANKING IN BANGLADESH: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS <i>Md. Shah Azam, Merina Yasmin and Nasrin Lubna</i>	30
RECENT TRENDS IN AUDIO CLASSIFICATION FOR RETRIEVAL APPLICATIONS <i>P.Dhanalakshmi, S.Palanivel and V.Ramalingam</i>	41
PESTER POWER EFFECT OF ADVERTISING <i>G Hari Sundar and Anoop Das</i>	47
TO BLAME OR NOT TO <i>K. Gayathri</i>	56
CYBER TERRORISM VULNERABILITY & IT'S DETERRENCE <i>G.S.Subashini and V.Sumathy</i>	58
CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION IN MEDIA BUSINESS: A PARADIGM SHIFT IN NEWSPAPER MARKETING <i>Dr. Neeta Inamdar</i>	62
PRODUCT INVOLVEMENT AND INTRINSIC ATTRIBUTES IN PURCHASE DECISION <i>J.Tamilselvi and Dr.C.Madhavi</i>	67
INFLUENCE OF INVOLVEMENT ON BRAND LOYALTY: AN EMPIRICAL EXAMINATION <i>R. Sritharan, K. Tamizh Jyothi and Dr. C. SamudhraRajakumar</i>	74
FACTORS THAT LEAD TO ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS—A STUDY OF SELECT FIRMS <i>Ganesh Prasad Mishra, Najeeb Uzzamman Khan Sherwani and Kusum Lata Mishra</i>	82
SBI LIFE – A CASE STUDY <i>Sanjeev Bajaj and Divya Gupta</i>	90
LEADERSHIP CAPABILITY : A STUDY ON MEASUREMENT APPROACH <i>G Suri Babu, T Mohana Rao and Dr. Salma Ahmed</i>	97
SOCIAL LEARNING THEORY AND THE BHAGAVAT GITA: INDIAN MANAGEMENT THOUGHT <i>Dr. C. Chendroyaperumal</i>	105
MID-CAREER CRISIS-A MISSING LINK IN STRATEGY <i>Prof. B. R. Ananthan and V. K. Ranjith</i>	110
SHAREHOLDER VALUE INDEX FOR BANKS IN INDIA <i>Dr. P.Thirumalvalavan and K. Suniltha</i>	116
HOW SMES VALUE SUPPLY CHAIN INTEGRATION? <i>Erhan Ada, Oznur Yurt and Melike Demirbag Kaplan</i>	128
WOMEN ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH <i>Dr.B.Rajasekaran and S.Sandhya</i>	137
DOCTORAL DISSERTATION ABSTRACTS	141

CYBER TERRORISM VULNERABILITY & IT'S DETERRENCE

G.S.Subashini and V.Sumathy

Faculty Members, Department of Business Administration, Annamalai University
subaasai_2004@yahoo.co.in

Abstract: Cyber crime is an evil, augment with use of computers in homes and offices that leads to creation of computer-related crimes. The increased use of networks and the growth of the Internet have added to cyber crime rate. Using the Internet, it is possible for a person sitting in India to steal a computer resource in Britain using a computer situated in Japan as a launch pad for the attack. A cyber terrorist can also alter the formulas of medication in pharmaceutical manufacturing, disrupt the bank transactions, spreading virus to soft wares, mobile phones and the stock exchange. It is easy to tamper computer evidence, which could be physical or wireless by malicious programming code across a network. Hence, economic growth of a country may be affected due to cyber crime recurrence. This paper describes about types of cyber crime occurred in the past and present. It also explains how the organizations become vulnerable and preventive measures of cyber terrorism.

Keywords : Cyber Terrorism, Cyber Crime, Internet hackers

INTRODUCTION:

Cyber crime is the most complicated problem in the cyber world. "Cyber terrorism" means intentional use, without legally recognized authority, violence, disruption or interference against cyber systems, when it is likely that such use would result in death or injury of a person or persons, substantial damage to physical property, civil disorder, or significant economic harm (6). "Any criminal activity that use a computer either as an instrumentality, target or a means for perpetuating further crimes comes within the ambit of cyber crime", A generalized definition of cyber crime may be "unlawful acts where in the computer is either a tool or target or both"(3) Cyber crimes can be broadly classified in to three categories : against the i)individual person, ii)organisations iii)society .¹

There are three types of criminals associated in cyber crime are

i) Hackers: Use illegal methods to access a computer.

ii) Crackers: Programme to extract information and benefit from it.

iii) Stealers: Beg, borrow, steal passwords, etc.

Apart from hacking/ cracking, some of these criminals have even stolen the hardware itself. (5)

Computer Crimes

Terrorist exploits the computer to attempt the crime. Computer crime is

"Premeditated and intended misuse of computer technology, for gaining unauthorized access to computer systems and thereby causing irrecoverable damage to the information". Computer crimes are in the form of interruption of investigation, taking revenge and deterioration of documents.

Types of Cyber Crimes

Cyberspace is vital for major people, where some of anonymous criminals will make use of it for illegal activities. The stratagem may differ according to the type of organization. Various strategies are listed below

STRATEGIES POSSIBLE MANIFESTATION POTENTIAL EFFECT

Introducing 'worms' or viruses

Introduction of virus in software package, illegal entry by a hacker Loss of data ,cost of repairing.

Electronic Funds Transfer Fraud

Criminals alter or duplicated electronic money to obtain goods or funds Liability for falsified money. Replacing cost associated with a compromised system

Murder from remote place

A hospital could be attacked by Changing patient information . Dose of certain drugs is altered to kill the patient. To damage the hospital name or to kill the particular person.

Strategies Possible Manifestation Potential Effect

Cutting off communication

Criminals will cut of the communication signals between server and client. For example, cutting the communication between aircrafts and the tower at the airport could attack airlines.

Data loss, corrupting important files, Customers may discontinue the use of service the organizations cannot proceed further until they recover.

Unauthorized system access

Hacker's entry to internal systems, confidential information intercepted, corruption of data, systems crash. Loss of data, theft of information, cost of repairing. Perceived insecurity of bank systems.

Scattering misinformation

Spreading misinformation over the internet to many customers could attack the company. Customers may not prefer to use the product or service affected customers may leave to other products.

Cyber Crime Vulnerability

Human beings and computers are extremely vulnerable to cyber crimes. It's easler for the terrorist to steal the nation secrets from the computers than stealing the gold from the jewelry shop. There are various reasons for vulnerability which are listed below Information attacks on the military, central banks, electricity and

software companies would' lead to heavy loss. If the company did not take any preventive measures, Cyber terrorist are able to destroy the business between large corporations (business-to-business transactions) by connecting their internal database to the Internet (1). The confidential data's of the business organizations are stored in centralized data storage equipment, the data's relating to financial, customer details and the new technology used by the organizations are stolen by professionals appointed by their competitors.

Complexity of OS - The computers work on operating systems (OS) and these operating systems in turn are composed of millions of codes. Human mind is liable to commit mistakes and it is not possible that there might not be a lapse at any stage. The cyber criminals take advantage of these lacunas and penetrate into the computer systems. It is far easier to find weakness in existing systems rather than designing a secure operating system.

Personal revenge - A per
revenge on his/her peer, employer, etc., employee would represent the greatest threat in terms of computer crimes to organization. Granting extraordinary privileges to some staff in relations to the key functions and assets of the organizations become vulnerable.

Loss of evidence is a very common problem as all the data are regularly destroyed. During cyber crime further collection of data outside the territorial extent also paralyses this system of crime investigation.

The organizations are not updated with latest version of anti-virus software, so latest virus spread by the cyber-terrorist will easly affect the systems.

Statutory Provisions:

Self-protection is essential, but It's not sufficient to make cyberspace as a safe place to do business. The rules and regulations must also be enforced to curb cyber crime activities. Countries where legal protections are inadequate would not able to compete with other countries economy.

The first principle concerns the...
The second principle concerns the...
The third principle concerns the...

The fourth principle concerns the...
The fifth principle concerns the...

The sixth principle concerns the...
The seventh principle concerns the...

The eighth principle concerns the...
The ninth principle concerns the...

The tenth principle concerns the...
The eleventh principle concerns the...

The twelfth principle concerns the...
The thirteenth principle concerns the...

The fourteenth principle concerns the...
The fifteenth principle concerns the...

Continuation of system status

Continuation of system status...
The first principle concerns the...
The second principle concerns the...

The sixteenth principle concerns the...
The seventeenth principle concerns the...

The eighteenth principle concerns the...
The nineteenth principle concerns the...

The twentieth principle concerns the...
The twenty-first principle concerns the...

The twenty-second principle concerns the...
The twenty-third principle concerns the...

The twenty-fourth principle concerns the...
The twenty-fifth principle concerns the...

The twenty-sixth principle concerns the...
The twenty-seventh principle concerns the...

The twenty-eighth principle concerns the...
The twenty-ninth principle concerns the...

The thirtieth principle concerns the...
The thirty-first principle concerns the...

The thirty-second principle concerns the...
The thirty-third principle concerns the...

The thirty-fourth principle concerns the...
The thirty-fifth principle concerns the...

The thirty-sixth principle concerns the...
The thirty-seventh principle concerns the...

The thirty-eighth principle concerns the...
The thirty-ninth principle concerns the...

The fortieth principle concerns the...
The forty-first principle concerns the...

The Indian parliament considered that it is necessary to implement the resolution passed by the General Assembly (Model Law on Electronic Commerce) of the United Nations Commission on Trade Law. As a consequence of which the Information Technology Act 2000 was passed and enforced on 17th May 2000. *The basic purpose to incorporate the changes in these Acts is to make them compatible with the Act of 2000.* So that, they may regulate and control the affairs of the cyber world in an effective manner.

The Information Technology Act deals with the various cyber crimes in chapters IX & XI. The important sections are Ss. 43,65,66,67.

Section 43 in particular deals with the unauthorised access, downloading, virus attacks or any contaminant, causes damage, disruption, denial of access, interference with the service availed by a person. This section provide for a fine up to Rs. 1 Crore by way of remedy.

Section 65 deals with 'tampering with computer source documents' and provides for imprisonment up to 3 years or fine, which may extend up to 2 years or both.

Section 66 deals with 'hacking with computer system' and provides for imprisonment up to 3 years or fine, which may extend up to 2 years or both.

Further section 67 deals with publication of obscene material and provides for imprisonment up to a term of 10 years and also with fine up to Rs. 2 Lakhs. (4)

A detailed cyber crime laws (updated) for many countries have shown in the annexure. The penalties provided in updated criminal statutes vary widely. Mauritius, the Philippines, and the United States have stronger penalties than many other countries for convictions of covered cyber crimes (7).

Deterrence of cyber crime

Cyber crime is an immoral which grows rapidly and it's necessary to take steps which can reduce the rate of cyber crime. As the saying goes "prevention is better than cure" that is applicable here too. Although it is difficult to reduce the crime

rate in a global manner, but an organization can able to prevent the cyber crime by taking precautions given below

Network administrators should be very caution and configuration should be changed as soon as vulnerabilities become apparent.

The secured programs should be audited in regular intervals, so that the crimes can be monitored.

The files in the E-mail should be scanned before admittance.

Cyber criminals will think twice before attacking valued systems and information. It can be prevented by providing self-protection in the organizations. So, the organization should focus on implementing features are:

a) Cyber Security plans like addressing people, process, and technology issues.

b) Educate employees on security practices, tactics for the handling of sensitive data, records and transactions.

c) Incorporate robust security technology such as firewalls, anti-virus software,

Providing Authentication services throughout the organizations computer systems.(7)

Important document of the organizations should not be stored on the LAN or WAN, so that it can be prevented from disloyal employees in the organizations.

Organizations should update the latest anti-virus software and should keep the backup volumes of important data.

If every organization follows the above instructions, the cyber crime can be prevented from heavy loss.

Resolving that there is a need to protect transnational information infrastructures from attacks and improper utilization and to deter such conduct by means of appropriate penalties and technology (8).

CONCLUSION

Cyber crime cannot be stopped at once, but can be reduced only by awareness. The people using Internet should update their system with latest antivirus software and should know how to protect their systems from illegal access. The punishments and penalties for cyber criminals should be severe according to their offence. Based on the priority to enforcement and prevention for curbing the cyber crimes, would lead to a change of better economic and social effects accordingly. The country should update their laws to make it more effective to combat cyber crime.

References

1. Daniel Amor ,The E-business® evolution, Hewlett-Packard, Professional books edition 2000
2. V.C.Joshi ,e-finance log in to the future , Response books, edition 2004
3. CSI communications August 2004 pg 15-18.
4. <http://www.naavi.org/pati-Nagpal R. - What is Cyber Crime?>
5. http://www.naavi.org/pati/pati_cybercrimes_dec03.htm- CYBER CRIME by Parthasarathi Pati
6. <http://www.iwar.org.uk/law/resources/cybercrime/stanford/cisac-draft.htm>
7. <http://www.mcconnellinternational.com/services/cybercrime.htm>
8. http://cybercrime.planetindia.net computer_vulnerability.htm

ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY

Department of Business Administration

BEST PAPER AWARD

Best Paper Award is for the Best paper / case study published in "Annamalai Journal of Management". The papers published in "Annamalai Journal of Management" is automatically considered for the award and a sub-committee will select the best paper from the papers published.

The first author of best paper will be awarded with cash prize and citation.

At annual Leaders Lecture Programme Series (LLPS) inauguration on Feb. 15th, the award will be given for the best paper. An opportunity will be given to the first author to present the Best Paper during the LLPs and to have interaction with the participants.

Contact :

The Editor,
 "Annamalai Journal of Management",
 Department of Business Administration,
 Annamalai University, Annamalainagar - 608 002,
 Tamilnadu, INDIA
 e-mail : editor.auajm@yahoo.co.in
 Phone : 04144 - 238796 * 328